

MALINA (*RUBUS IDAEUS* L.) MEVALARINING BIOLOGIK, KIMYOVIY VA GENOMIK XUSUSIYATLARI BO‘YICHA ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur tezisdagi malina (*Rubus idaeus* L.) mevalarining biologik, oziqaviy va genetik xususiyatlari bo‘yicha adabiyotlar tahlil qilingan. Mevalar fenol birikmalar, antotsianlar, flavonoidlar va askorbin kislotasiga boy bo‘lib, yuqori antioksidant faollikka ega. Urug‘ yog‘i poliqonmagan yog‘ kislotalari va tokofeollarga boy bo‘lib, funksional oziq-ovqat va kosmetik mahsulotlarda qo‘llanilishi mumkin. Genomik tadqiqotlar *Rubus* turlarida yuqori genetik xilma-xillikni ko‘rsatadi. Mevalarning biologik, fitokimyoviy va genetik qiymati ularni seleksiya, funksional oziq-ovqat va dorivor mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarishda qadrlash imkonini beradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: malina, *Rubus idaeus* L., biologik qiymat, fitokimyo, antioksidant, fenol birikmalar, genetik xilma-xillik, urug‘ yog‘i.

Аннотация: В данной работе проведён анализ литературы по биологическим, пищевым и генетическим характеристикам плодов малины (*Rubus idaeus* L.). Плоды богаты фенольными соединениями, антоцианами, флавоноидами и аскорбиновой кислотой, обладая высокой антиоксидантной активностью. Масло семян малины

содержит ненасыщенные жирные кислоты и токоферолы, что позволяет его использовать в функциональных пищевых и косметических продуктах. Геномные исследования показывают высокий уровень генетического разнообразия у видов *Rubus*. Высокая биологическая, фитохимическая и генетическая ценность малины делает её перспективной для селекции, функционального питания и создания лекарственных продуктов.

Ключевые слова: малина, *Rubus idaeus* L., биологическая ценность, фитохимия, антиоксидант, фенольные соединения, генетическое разнообразие, масло семян.

Abstract: This study provides a literature analysis of the biological, nutritional, and genetic characteristics of raspberry fruits (*Rubus idaeus* L.). The fruits are rich in phenolic compounds, anthocyanins, flavonoids, and ascorbic acid, exhibiting strong antioxidant activity. Raspberry seed oil contains unsaturated fatty acids and tocopherols, making it valuable for functional food and cosmetic applications. Genomic studies reveal a high level of genetic diversity in *Rubus* species. The high biological, phytochemical, and genetic value of raspberry fruits makes them promising for breeding, functional food production, and medicinal product development.

Keywords: raspberry, *Rubus idaeus* L., biological value, phytochemistry, antioxidant, phenolic compounds, genetic diversity, seed oil.

Kirish

So‘nggi yillarda *Rubus* jinsiga mansub o‘simliklar, xususan malina (*Rubus idaeus* L.) turlari biologik faol moddalarga boyligi, yuqori

antioksidant faolligi hamda genetik xilma-xilligi bilan ilmiy tadqiqotlar markaziga aylandi. Malina nafaqat qimmatli oziq-ovqat manbai, balki funktsional va dorivor ahamiyatga ega bo‘lgan o‘simlik sifatida ham qaralmoqda (Kähkönen *et al.*, 2001; Lopez-Corona *et al.*, 2022).

Malina mevalarining fitokimyoviy va antioksidant xususiyatlari - Ko‘plab tadqiqotlarda malina mevalari fenol birikmalar, antotsianlar, flavonoidlar va askorbin kislotaning muhim manbai ekanligi ko‘rsatilgan. Kähkönen *et al.* (2001) hamda Pantelidis *et al.* (2007) tadqiqotlariga ko‘ra, malina mevalaridagi fenol moddalar yuqori antioksidant faollikka ega bo‘lib, erkin radikallarni neytrallashtirishda muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Yovvoyi va madaniy malina navlarini solishtirgan Cekiç va Özgen (2010) tadqiqotlarida yovvoyi malina mevalarida antioksidant quvvat va fitokimyoviy moddalar miqdori yuqoriroq ekani aniqlangan. Shuningdek, Kafkas *et al.* (2008) turli navlarda yog‘ kislotalari va fenol tarkibining sezilarli farq qilishini ta’kidlagan.

Malina urug‘i yog‘i va biologik ahamiyati-Malina urug‘idan olinadigan yog‘ ham alohida ilmiy qiziqish uyg‘otmoqda. Oomah *et al.* (2000) va Ispiryan *et al.* (2021) tadqiqotlarida malina urug‘i yog‘i poliqonmagan yog‘ kislotalari, tokoferollar va biologik faol moddalarga boy ekani ko‘rsatilgan. Bu xususiyatlar uni funktsional oziq-ovqat va kosmetik mahsulotlarda qo‘llash imkonini beradi.

Genomik tadqiqotlar va filogenetik tahlillar-So‘nggi yillarda *Rubus* jinsida xloroplast genomlarini o‘rganishga oid tadqiqotlar keskin ortdi. Davik *et al.* (2022) tomonidan malina uchun xromosoma darajasidagi to‘liq genom yig‘ilishi taqdim etilgan bo‘lib, bu selektsiya va evolyutsion tadqiqotlar uchun muhim asos hisoblanadi. *Rubus* turlarining xloroplast

genomlari Han *et al.* (2023), Liu *et al.* (2021), Wang *et al.* (2020), Yang *et al.* (2017; 2022) va Yu *et al.* (2022) ishlarida o‘rganilgan bo‘lib, ular *Rubus* jinsida yuqori darajada genetik xilma-xillik mavjudligini ko‘rsatadi. Filogenetik tahlillarda MAFFT, RAxML, DnaSP va Geneious kabi bioinformatik dasturlar keng qo‘llanilgan (Kato & Standley, 2013; Stamatakis, 2014; Rozas *et al.*, 2017; Kearse *et al.*, 2012). MISA-web va NOVOPlasty dasturlari esa mikrosatellitlarni aniqlash va organella genomlarini yig‘ishda samarali ekani isbotlangan (Beier *et al.*, 2017; Dierckxsens *et al.*, 2017).

Sog‘liq uchun ahamiyati -Malina mevalaridagi fenol birikmalar antioksidant, yallig‘lanishga qarshi va tsitotoksik xususiyatlarga ega ekani ko‘plab ilmiy manbalarda qayd etilgan (Lopez-Corona *et al.*, 2022). Bu xususiyatlar malina mevalarini yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari, onkologik va metabolik kasalliklar profilaktikasida muhim funktsional mahsulot sifatida baholash imkonini beradi.

Xulosa

Adabiyotlar tahlili shuni ko‘rsatadiki, malina (*Rubus idaeus* L.) mevalari yuqori biologik, fitokimyoviy va genetik qiymatga ega bo‘lgan o‘simlik hisoblanadi. Antioksidant faollik, boy fenol tarkib hamda genomik ma’lumotlar malina seleksiyasi, funktsional oziq-ovqat ishlab chiqarish va dorivor mahsulotlar yaratish uchun keng istiqbollarni ochib beradi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO‘YXATI:

1. Beier, S., Thiel, T., Münch, T., Scholz, U., & Mascher, M. (2017). MISA-web: a web server for microsatellite prediction. *Bioinformatics*, 33(16), 2583–2585.

2.Carter, K. A., Liston, A., Bassil, N. V., Alice, L. A., Bushakra, J. M., Sutherland, B. L., Mockler, T. C., Bryant, D. W., & Hummer, K. E. (2019). Target capture sequencing unravels *Rubus* evolution. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 10, 1615.

3.Čekić, C., & Özgen, M. (2010). Comparison of antioxidant capacity and phytochemical properties of wild and cultivated red raspberries (*Rubus idaeus* L.). *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis*, 23(6), 540–544.

4.Davik, J., Røen, D., Lysøe, E., Buti, M., Rossman, S., Alsheikh, M., Aiden, E. L., Dudchenko, O., & Sargent, D. J. (2022). A chromosome-level genome sequence assembly of the red raspberry (*Rubus idaeus* L.). *PLoS ONE*, 17(3), e0265096.

5.Dierckxsens, N., Mardulyn, P., & Smits, G. (2017). NOVOPlasty: de novo assembly of organelle genomes from whole genome data. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 45(4), e18.

6.Han, Y., Tong, L., Zhang, Z., Yang, S., & Yang, F. (2023). The complete chloroplast genome sequence of *Rubus irritans* Focke (Rosaceae). *Mitochondrial DNA Part B: Resources*, 8(1), 177–180.

7.Ispiryan, A., Viškelis, J., & Viškelis, P. (2021). Red raspberry (*Rubus idaeus* L.) seed oil: a review. *Plants*, 10(5), 944.

8.Kähkönen, M. P., Hopia, A. I., & Heinonen, M. (2001). Berry phenolics and their antioxidant activity. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 49(8), 4076–4082.

9.Kafkas, E., Özgen, M., Özogul, Y., & Türemiş, N. (2008). Phytochemical and fatty acid profile of selected red raspberry cultivars: a comparative study. *Journal of Food Quality*, 31(1), 67–78. Katoh, K., & Standley, D. M. (2013). MAFFT multiple sequence alignment software

version 7: improvements in performance and usability. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 30(4), 772–780

10. Kearse, M., Moir, R., Wilson, A., et al. (2012). Geneious Basic: an integrated and extendable desktop software platform for the organization and analysis of sequence data. *Bioinformatics*, 28(12), 1647–1649.

11. Lopez-Corona, A. V., Valencia-Espinosa, I., González-Sánchez, F. A., Sánchez-López, A. L., Garcia-Amezquita, L. E., & Garcia-Varela, R. (2022). Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and cytotoxic activity of phenolic compounds extracted from raspberries (*Rubus idaeus*): A general review. *Antioxidants*, 11(6), 1192.

12. Oomah, B. D., Ladet, S., Godfrey, D. V., Liang, J., & Girard, B. (2000). Characteristics of raspberry (*Rubus idaeus* L.) seed oil. *Food Chemistry*, 69(2), 187–193.

13. Pantelidis, G. E., Vasilakakis, M., Manganaris, G. A., & Diamantidis, G. (2007). Antioxidant capacity, phenol, anthocyanin and ascorbic acid contents in berries. *Food Chemistry*, 102(3), 777–783.

14. Rozas, J., Ferrer-Mata, A., Sánchez-DelBarrio, J. C., et al. (2017). DnaSP 6: DNA sequence polymorphism analysis of large data sets. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 34(12), 3299–3302.

15. Stamatakis, A. (2014). RAxML version 8: a tool for phylogenetic analysis and post-analysis of large phylogenies. *Bioinformatics*, 30(9), 1312–1313.